

ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT METHODS FOR CROWDING OF ANTERIOR TEETH

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Abstract

The issue of anterior teeth (AT) crowding in patients of different ages has been studied, and orthodontic treatment (OT) methods for such cases are described. Clinical examinations were conducted on 47 patients aged 8 to 25 years. A combination of surgical and orthodontic treatment methods is advisable at an older age. However, when diagnosing macrodontia of erupted incisors at the early stages of tooth replacement, the method of sequential tooth extraction can be applied.

Keywords: *deciduous teeth, dental crowding, anterior teeth, macrodontia, microdontia, third molar, orthodontic treatment.*

One of the most common malocclusions is dental crowding (DC) in the anterior (frontal) region of the lower jaw (LJ). To date, some questions remain controversial regarding the etiopathogenetic factors contributing to the development of crowded positioning of the lower anterior teeth (CPLAT) at different age stages, as well as the relationship between the abnormal positioning of the lower jaw's third molars and DC in the anterior region [1-3].

Objective of the Study:

To investigate CPLAT in pediatric and adult patients and conduct orthodontic treatment (OT) for them.

Materials and Methods:

A clinical examination was conducted on 47 patients aged 8 to 25 years. The condition of 36 lower third molar (TM) buds in patients with CPLAT was studied on panoramic radiographs over time, both before and after OT. Summarizing the results of clinical, biometric, and radiological examinations of patients with CPLAT, it can be hypothesized that this pathology represents one of the manifestations of the early stages of a general reduction in the dentoalveolar system (DAS).

This is supported primarily by the high prevalence of CPLAT, ranging from $56.5 \pm 5.4\%$ in the 8–14 age group to $61.6 \pm 10.3\%$ in the 17–25 age group. The increase in the relative frequency of this pathology with age by 5.1% indicates the presence of "risk factors" leading to late-onset DC and DAS reduction.

Results and Discussion:

Both endogenous and exogenous etiological factors influence this pathology. The significant contribution of endogenous factors (individual macrodontia, small oral vestibule, short lingual frenulum) suggests a hereditary nature of CPLAT. In older age groups, the etiology remained unexplained in 42% of cases, indicating the possible existence of other causes contributing to "late-onset" DC. In the presented concept of etiopathogenetic factors contributing to the development of CPLAT, a significant role is attributed to the influence of endogenous (hereditary) factors and the

"functional underload" of the DAS in modern humans overall.

Biometric studies of jaw models with CPLAT revealed a high percentage (94%) of deformation in the dentoalveolar arch and the apical base of the lower jaw (LJ), regardless of the severity of DC. This is also corroborated by the symptom of general underdevelopment of the LJ.

Examining the condition and position of TMs on the LJ in the studied patient group, retention and a lack of space for proper alignment were noted in 96% of cases. Measurements of the inclination angle of the TM's longitudinal axis relative to the second molar, conducted dynamically before and after OT using bracket systems [as per R. Evans, 1988], showed variations from 8° – 58° to 20° – 63° , respectively. These findings indicate an incompatibility with normal or uncomplicated eruption [5].

In children with deciduous teeth, narrowing of the dental arch (DA) during the transition period is corrected using plate appliances with screws. For uniform narrowing of the DA, it is advisable to position the orthodontic screw in the middle of the DA, in the premolar region. If the DA is significantly narrowed, two screws may be used.

For cases with a deep palate, a Coffin spring plate is used. If the narrowing occurs in the anterior or posterior section of the dental arch (DA), the screw is placed accordingly. For significant narrowing of the anterior section of the upper DA, an expansion screw is positioned near the canines, while a limiter is placed in the lateral section.

In cases combining DA narrowing with protrusion of the upper anterior teeth, a plate appliance with a screw and vestibular arch is used. To normalize the DA shape in children with deciduous teeth or during their replacement, a plate with a screw and a sectoral cut in the incisor region is recommended. For the lower jaw (LJ), a plate with two screws is applied, positioned near the canines and the first primary molars or premolars.

If the anterior section of the upper DA is shortened, Byinin or Schwartz splints may be used as indicated. In children with permanent teeth, the DA can be widened and lengthened using fixed appliances, such as the Angle arch or a bracket system. Alongside forward tooth movement, teeth can also be rotated around their longitudinal axes.

Shortening of one or both lateral sections of the DA often results in a lack of space for premolars and canines, even when the anterior section of the DA is of proper width and length [2, 3].

In children older than 12 years, an Angle sliding arch can be used. The treatment outcome depends not only on the degree of deformation but also on the extent of overlap between antagonist teeth. Even with proper overlap depth, increasing the DA size is possible only by separating the DA in the specific section.

One common anomaly of the DA is its discontinuity. Gaps (diastemas) between incisors and canines are considered normal only in children aged 4 to 6 years. At any other age, the DA is considered abnormal if there are no contacts between the proximal surfaces of adjacent teeth. Diastemas can occur due to tooth agenesis, retention, or a reduction in tooth size. These anomalies are often accompanied by displacement of neighboring teeth.

If the gaps are minor and aesthetically acceptable, OT may not be required. However, in cases of tooth retention, eruption outside the DA, or lack of space due to displaced adjacent teeth, space must be created. In cases of microdontia, agenesis, or tooth retention, gaps are closed using crowns or removable plate dentures.

The DA structure is also considered abnormal in cases of crowded teeth positioning. Due to insufficient space in the DA, teeth may rotate around their vertical axis or be positioned outside the DA.

In cases of macrodontia and DC, aligning the teeth to their proper positions via orthodontic methods is impossible. Extraction of one or two teeth is necessary,

typically premolars, to create space for proper positioning of canines and incisors.

A combination of surgical and orthodontic treatment methods is advisable at an older age. However, when diagnosing macrodontia of erupted incisors at the early stages of tooth replacement, the sequential tooth extraction method proposed by Hotz can be employed. This involves the removal of one or both primary canines, depending on the size of the crowns of the permanent incisors. This approach facilitates the proper alignment of permanent incisors.

After the eruption of permanent premolars, these are also extracted to create space for the correct subsequent eruption of permanent canines. In some cases, timely application of this method can eliminate the need for OT or significantly reduce its extent [2, 5].

Thus, the findings of this study confirm the presence of a general reduction in the DAS under modern conditions, one of the manifestations of which is CPLAT. Upon identifying this pathology, timely OT in patients is essential.

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